

Philippine Science High School
Main Campus

An Artificial Neural Network Model on River
Water Level Prediction in the St. Nino
Station of the Marikina River

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Station of the Marikina River

by

Christian Philip L. Gelera
Christine Joy C. Okubo
Angelika Joie S. Tagupa

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ABSTRACT

The Marikina River is prone to overbanking during heavy rainfall common in the Philippines. This causes flooding to its catch basin and severely affects major metropolitan cities around it — causing loss of life, property, and resources. This study aims to develop a prediction model on the Marikina River water level based on real-time precipitation, temperature, and previous day water level in the Sto. Nino station of the river. The prediction model makes use of a Backpropagation Neural Network with a sigmoid normalization function. Daily precipitation, temperature, and water level of Manila from 2001-2015 were acquired from the Philippine Atmospheric, Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA) to provide a training dataset for the model. During training, this dataset was used as input for the model and its outputs were back-propagated into the hidden layer to calibrate the program. From the final testing ($n = 100$), the model produced a percent error less than 2.5% and a correlation coefficient of 0.77 or better for 10 hidden layers, 1500 iterations, 0.3 learning rate, and 0.1 momentum. The produced values indicate consistency and satisfactory correlation of the most successful model for a small sampling size. This suggests the viability of Backpropagation Neural Networks to be developed into an accurate, robust, and adaptable prediction model for the Marikina River water level, and other hydrological events.

APPROVAL SHEET

This research work entitled, “An Artificial Neural Network Model on River Water Level Prediction in the St. Nino Station of the Marikina River” by Christian Philip L. Gelera, Christine Joy C. Okubo, and Angelika Joie S. Tagupa, presented to the Faculty of the Philippine Science High School – Main Campus in partial fulfillment of the requirements in Science and Technology Research 1, is hereby accepted.

Sir Mark Louie D. Lopez
Research Adviser

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INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Flood is a recurring and often catastrophic natural disaster frequently experienced in the Philippines. It leads to thousands of lives and billions of pesos lost. Short-lived floods and its effects like heavy traffic costs the Philippine economy 2.4 billion pesos per day (Galang, 2013). Metro Manila, being an urban area, experiences urban flooding. Urban flooding is a flood caused by the inefficiency or overwhelming of drainages in urban areas. Urban areas mostly do not have open soil which other areas use for water storage; thus precipitation must be collected in sewage systems through drains. However, drains are affected by man-made factors, such as clogging of waste material and ageing drainage infrastructure. Through exhaustive reading of research journals, we encountered a study titled *A Backpropagation Neural Network Model on Precipitation Level Prediction* (Co, 2012). We thought that if it was possible to predict precipitation level from noisy data such as previous records of precipitation levels, humidity, rain indication, sea level pressure, temperature, and maximum sustained wind speed, then maybe it is possible to predict flood water levels in the metro from the precipitation level predictions and drainage systems.

Statement of the Problem

We aim to create a neural network model that is able to predict the floodwater level of the Pasig-Marikina River. We chose this area because this river has many tributaries that encompass Metro Manila and the flooding of this river will have repercussions throughout a very large region.

Significance of the Study

Floods are one of the most devastating natural disasters in the Philippines. It is believed that the damaging impact of flooding on human lives is “related to the warning-time given before a flood occurs.” (Hughes, Greenwood, Coulson, & Blair, 2006). Early prediction of flooding plays an important role in reducing the consequences and risks, for these flood control measures reduces effects of flood water to property. According to the World Meteorological Organization, the increasing frequency of heavy rain, together with changes in upstream land-use and an increase in population and assets in flood prone areas, greatly contribute in the increase of flood effects (2006). Using these factors to predict flood levels will help warn the public about the expected flood intensity and remind them to prepare against possible vulnerabilities, thus lessening the cost of damage.

Scope and Limitations

The success of our study will also aid in the development of quantitative and objective flood warning systems based on the predicted floodwater level. Our research requires the assessment of drainage systems and flood control plans and may suggest improvement to the government agencies responsible for the development and maintenance of these. We aim to succeed in this study to fulfill these significance.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

I. The Marikina River

The Marikina River is a significant river system in the Philippines.

The Marikina River stretches 27 kilometers at its longest path. Cities surrounding it are Marikina, San Mateo, Quezon City, and Pasig (Tuddao, 2011). Most of the floodwater in this river are runoff water from the slopes of Sierra Madre. The river system drains to bodies of water in southern Luzon such as the Laguna Lake and Manila Bay making it a major tributary.

The Pasig-Marikina River Basin is located east of Metropolitan Manila and has a total drainage area of 377.82 sq. kilometers. It is surrounded by urban communities that are prone to flooding and disasters. This basin is the source of flood waters that inundates low-lying areas surrounding it (Badilla, 2008).

There are fifteen water level sensor stations along the river watersheds. There are two sets of stations: (1) maintained by the Philippine Atmospheric Geophysical and Astronomical Services Administration (PAGASA) and (2) maintained by the Metro Manila Development Authority. River water level data monitoring is available in the PAGASA site. These data are being used in prediction using flood modelling. (Badilla, R., 2017, February 16, Personal interview with Socrates Paat of the PAGASA Hydrometeorology Division).

Flooding due to river water-level rise negatively affects its victims.

The Pasig-Marikina River is prone to overbanking when there is heavy rainfall (Muto, Morishita, & Syson, 2012). This causes flooding to the Pasig-Marikina catch basin and severely affects the cities around it. Floods have tangible and intangible effects. Its immediate effects, which we can observe, are human casualties, loss of property and livestock, and deterioration of infrastructure. Annually, the Philippines loses an average of \$545.43 million dollars due to floods (UNISDR, n.d.). Floods can also affect its victims psychologically (Office of the Queensland Chief Scientist, 2011).

II. Machine Learning

Machine Learning is the creation of an artificial intelligence for automating processes.

An ANN is configured for a specific application, such as pattern recognition or data classification, through a learning process. Learning in ANNs involves adjustments to the connections that exist between the neurons similar to how it is in biological systems (Stergiou & Siganos). Machine learning is a way of creating Artificial Intelligence (A. I.) through improving the performance of a machine. Its goal is to automate by building special-purpose systems (Nilsson, 2005).

Algorithms are a major component of machine learning.

Machine learning requires an algorithm to function. There are six types of algorithms based on how they handle given inputs: (1) supervised learning, (2) unsupervised learning, (3) semi-supervised learning, (4) reinforcement learning, (5) transduction, and (6) learning to learn. These algorithms may further be classified into multiple learning methods based on the analysis and mathematical presentation of data (Ayodele, 2010).

III. Neural Networks

Neural Networks are computer algorithms designed to think like the brain.

An Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is an information processing paradigm that is inspired by the way biological nervous systems, such as the brain, process information (Stergiou & Siganos). The computations of the brain are done by a highly interconnected network of neurons, which communicate by sending electric pulses through the neural wiring consisting of axons, synapses and dendrites (Krogh, 2008).

Neural networks are primarily used for classification, prediction, clustering, and association. It is able to find complex patterns between seemingly unrelated objects and make predictions given nonlinear data (Hall, Brooks, & Doswell, 1998).

Neural Networks require numerous components to function.

The neurons in an artificial neural network are input, hidden, and output nodes. Neural networks can have any number of layers, and any number of nodes per layer. The input nodes are passive and do not modify the data. These propagate single-value parameters to the hidden layers. The action of the neural network is determined by the weights placed on the hidden and output nodes (Smith, 2011).

Activation functions, also called Transfer functions, define the output of a hidden layer node given an input or a set of inputs. It is the mathematical function that translates the inputs to output. The mapping capabilities of a NN are strictly related to the nonlinear component found in the activation function of the neurons (Lozito, Francesco, & Salvini,

2015). Nonlinear activation functions enable the neural network to produce nonlinear outputs from a wide range of data.

Six commonly used activation functions are: (1) Unit step or threshold functions, (2) Signum functions, (3) Linear functions, (4) Piecewise linear functions, (5) logistic sigmoid functions, (6) hyperbolic tangent or tanh functions. These functions have a range of $[0, +1]$ or $[-1, +1]$. Sigmoids symmetric about the origin are preferred because these are likely to produce outputs close to zero on average.

Table 1. Commonly used Activation functions

Activation function	Equation	Example	1D Graph
Unit step (Heaviside)	$\phi(z) = \begin{cases} 0, & z < 0, \\ 0.5, & z = 0, \\ 1, & z > 0, \end{cases}$	Perceptron variant	
Sign (Signum)	$\phi(z) = \begin{cases} -1, & z < 0, \\ 0, & z = 0, \\ 1, & z > 0, \end{cases}$	Perceptron variant	
Linear	$\phi(z) = z$	Adaline, linear regression	
Piece-wise linear	$\phi(z) = \begin{cases} 1, & z \geq \frac{1}{2}, \\ z + \frac{1}{2}, & -\frac{1}{2} < z < \frac{1}{2}, \\ 0, & z \leq -\frac{1}{2}, \end{cases}$	Support vector machine	
Logistic (sigmoid)	$\phi(z) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-z}}$	Logistic regression, Multi-layer NN	
Hyperbolic tangent	$\phi(z) = \frac{e^z - e^{-z}}{e^z + e^{-z}}$	Multi-layer NN	

Normalization of data scales the parameter inputs of different units to the range of the activation function which is either $[0, +1]$ or $[-1, +1]$. It is applied to all layers because the outputs of each node that are inputs in the next layer should be close to zero and within the

range (Lecun, Bottou, Orr, & Muller, 2002). The two most commonly used normalization functions are: (1) Min-max normalization, and (2) Mean-variance normalization.

Min-max normalization is a linear type of normalization that uses the minimum and maximum of both the initial and scaled data set. Mean-variance normalization normalizes the data to have mean of 0 and unit variance or 0.5 for nonlinear normalization. It is easier to convert to the [0, 1] range of most activation functions (Seide, Li, & Yu, 2011).

A Backpropagation Neural Network back propagates the produced error of the network.

Figure 1. A Backpropagation Neural Network model

Backpropagation learning algorithm works for feed-forward networks with continuous output. Training starts by setting all the weights in the network to small random numbers. The training data is made into an input example and gets an output from the network. The difference between the produced output and the desired output is expressed as an error. It back propagates the error to adjust the weights and train the NN (Krogh, 2008).

Designing and training a network using backpropagation involves arbitrary choices such as the number and types of nodes, layers, learning rates, training and test sets, and so forth. These factors are critical but there is usually no objective way of deciding them because they are largely problem-based and data dependent (Lecun, Bottou, Orr, & Muller, 2002).

Multiple parameters and factors can be tweaked in order to optimize a neural network.

To optimize the NN, the number of input nodes, hidden layers, and output nodes are to be considered. The choice of parameters, number of iterations, momentum, learning rate, and weight decay are also factors that can be modified. Since there are no specific rules on determining these, process control is needed to find the number of layers that will give the desired accuracy.

Insufficient hidden layers may cause unnecessary training time while too much may cause overtraining. Too much or too little inputs and the correlation of these parameters will affect the accuracy of the model. The number of iterations, momentum, learning rate, and weight decay will affect the testing time. The ideal and appropriate number of these factors can only be found by testing the model and getting the error (Orr, Schraudolph, & Cummins, 1999).

Neural networks are widely used in making predictions.

Neural networks have significantly better prediction qualities than standard and statistical models which maximizes its potential in forecasting. (Falát, L., 2016) The neural network model is a more effective method for mapping the nonlinear relationship of predictors and the predictand than the traditional linear statistical method. It is widely used in climate and disaster predictions for this reason. (Muhlbauer, Spichtinger, & Lohmann, 2009)

Neural networks are currently developed and widely used for nonlinear relationships and weather predictions such as precipitation level, storm surge, and flood water level predictions. (Atita et. al., 1999) Short-range data from weather and atmospheric conditions are often nonlinear and

discontinuous, but neural networks have the ability to organize these data to find patterns and relationships in order to make predictions. (Hill, O'Connor, & Remus, 1996)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Overview

The research aims to predict river water level of the Pasig-Marikina River using historical data from 2000 to 2015. Important steps in the process include data acquisition and organization, deriving the activation functions and weights for the model, coding the artificial neural network, optimization, testing the architectures, and performing statistical tests.

Acquiring of Data

Daily precipitation, temperature, and water level of Manila from 2000-2015 are the inputs of our model and are all acquired from PAGASA Science Garden and Hydrometeorology Division in Agham Road, Diliman, Quezon City. Catch basins and tributaries of the Pasig-Marikina River were obtained from the Metro Manila Development's office along EDSA. All above collected data are compiled into an excel sheet. These will be tabulated and put into a CSV format that can be interpreted by Python (Co, 2012).

Coding of the Artificial Neural Network

Co (2012), in his study titled "Backpropagation of a Neural Network Model for Precipitation Prediction in the Philippines" used noisy data in his neural networks. He made two neural networks; one has one hidden layer and the other has two hidden layers. Another neural network will be added and will make use of three hidden layers. Also, the input data used in the original code will be replaced by the data the group will have gathered. We will use the same activation function (sigmoid function) and normalization function that Co used.

The code also has four modules separate from the neural network itself. The first module will serve as a modem for the program to analyze the data compiled in Excel. The second will normalize the data to efficiently organize the data using mean-variance normalization. Normalization is a way to efficiently organize numerical data into the range [0,1] which can be easily processed by the computer. Mean-variance normalization is used to normalize data that do not follow a linear pattern and contains extreme values. The third will graph the acquired and predicted data, and the fourth will compute for the correlation coefficient and root mean square of the network. These modules will also be used in our code.

Testing of Neural Network and Analysis

Deshpande and Khan (2012) used the mean square error, normalized mean square error, and correlation coefficient in testing the performance of their neural network. The group will compare the output of the neural networks' prediction for flood levels in the past years with actual flood levels; the mean square error, normalized mean square error, and correlation coefficient will be determined. The model to be labelled as the best among the others tested will be the neural network with the highest correlation coefficient of at least 0.8 and the lowest root mean square.

Table 2. Materials needed

Protocol	Material	Specifications	Amount	Cost	Source	Date of Certification
K, L, M	Python	Version 3.5.2	3	-	See attached	See Figure 2

E, F, N	Mathplotlib		3	-	Mathplotlib.com	See Figure 3
A, B, D	Data on actual flood water level and precipitation levels in EDSA Quezon City from 2000 to 2016	Daily data from 2000-2016	1	-	MMDA/Science Garden	See Figures 4-5
C	Drainage efficiency of each day of 2000-2015 of EDSA Quezon City	Daily data from 2000-2016	1	-	DPWH	See Figures 4-5
K, L	Source Code for Artificial Neural Network model	Based on Neil Schemenauer's Backpropagation Neural Network Code	1	-	Python online source code library	See Figure 6

Table 3. Equipment needed

Protocol	Material	Specifications	Amount	Cost
E, F, I, J, K, L, M, N, Q, R	Computer	with Python 3.5.2 and Mathplotlib	3	-

Figure 2: Python Software

matplotlib

[home](#) | [examples](#) | [gallery](#) | [pyplot](#) | [docs](#) » [User's Guide](#) » [Configuration Guide](#) »

Installing

There are many different ways to install matplotlib, and the best way depends on what operating system you are using, what you already have installed, and how you want to use it. To avoid wading through all the details (and potential complications) on this page, there are several convenient options.

Installing pre-built packages

Most platforms : scientific Python distributions

The first option is to use one of the pre-packaged python distributions that already provide matplotlib built-in. The Continuum.io Python distribution ([Anaconda](#) or [miniconda](#)) and the Enthought distribution ([Canopy](#)) are both excellent choices that "just work" out of the box for Windows, OSX and common Linux platforms. Both of these distributions include matplotlib and *lots* of other useful tools.

Linux : using your package manager

If you are on Linux, you might prefer to use your package manager. matplotlib is packaged for almost every major Linux distribution.

- Debian / Ubuntu : `sudo apt-get install python-matplotlib`
- Fedora / Redhat : `sudo yum install python-matplotlib`

Figure 3: Matplotlib Software

Figure 4: Data Gathering From PAGASA

From: Montaño, Charmaine A.
Sent: Monday, December 12, 2016 12:17 PM
To: 'ggelatin@gmail.com'
Cc: Navarro, Mary Rose E.; Santiago, Andro V.; Villar, Maria Mildred A.
Subject:

Good day!

Thank you for contacting us.

With regards to your concern, you can contact our Unified Project Management Office (UPMO)- Flood Control Management Cluster since your query falls under their purview. You can reach them at telephone number 304-3813 and kindly look for Ms. Jane Batulan.

Thank you.

Regards,

Mary Rose E. Navarro
 Community Affairs Officer I

Regards,

Charmaine A. Montaño
 Administrative Assistant VI
 Stakeholders Management Section, Stakeholders Affairs Division, Stakeholders Relations Service
 Department of Public Works and Highways
 Tel. # Direct Line (02) 304.3275; Local No. 43275 | www.dpwh.gov.ph

Figure 5: Data Gathering from DPWH


```

    revert(target, predicted)
    statTest(target, predicted)
    PlotResults(target, predicted, len(pat2))

# Back-Propagation Neural Networks
#
# Written in Python. See http://www.python.org/
# Placed in the public domain.
# Neil Schemenauer <nas@arctrix.com>

import math
import random
import string
import sys

random.seed(0)

# calculate a random number where: a <- rand < b
def rand(a, b):
    return (b-a)*random.random() + a

# Make a matrix (we could use NumPy to speed this up)
def makeMatrix(i, j, fill=0.0):
    m = []
    for i in range(i):
        m.append([fill]*j)
    return m

# our sigmoid function, tanh is a little nicer than the standard 1/(1+e^-x)
def sigmoid(x):
    return math.tanh(x)

# derivative of our sigmoid function, in terms of the output (i.e. y)
def dsigmoid(y):
    return 1.0 - y**2

class NN:
    def __init__(self, ni, nh, no):
        # number of input, hidden, and output nodes
        self.ni = ni + 1 # +1 for bias node
        self.nh = nh
        self.no = no

        # activations for nodes
        self.ai = [1.0]*self.ni
        self.ah = [1.0]*self.nh
        self.ao = [1.0]*self.no

        # create weights
        self.wi = makeMatrix(self.ni, self.nh)
        self.wo = makeMatrix(self.nh, self.no)
        # set them to random values
        for i in range(self.ni):
            for j in range(self.nh):
                self.wi[i][j] = rand(-0.2, 0.2)
        for j in range(self.nh):
            for k in range(self.no):
                self.wo[j][k] = rand(-2.0, 2.0)

        # last change in weights for momentum
        self.wi = makeMatrix(self.ni, self.nh)
        self.wo = makeMatrix(self.nh, self.no)

    def update(self, inputs):
        if len(inputs) != self.ni-1:
            raise ValueError('wrong number of inputs')

        # input activations
        for i in range(self.ni-1):
            #self.ai[i] = sigmoid(inputs[i])
            self.ai[i] = inputs[i]

```

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```

# momentum factor
for i in range(itacations):
    error = 0.0
    for p in patterns:
        inputs = p[0]
        targets = p[1]
        self.update(inputs)
        error = error + self.backpropagate(targets, N, M)
    if i % 100 == 0:
        print('error %-.5f' % error)

def demo():
    # Teach network XOR function
    pat = [
        [[0,0], [0]],
        [[0,1], [1]],
        [[1,0], [1]],
        [[1,1], [0]]
    ]

    # create a network with two input, two hidden, and one output nodes
    n = NN(2, 2, 1)
    # train it with some patterns
    n.train(pat)
    # test it
    n.test(pat)

if __name__ == '__main__':
    demo()

```

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Figure 6: Source Code for Artificial Neural Network Model

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the Neural Network

Table 1 shows the produced error of the neural network based on different parameters that were adjusted for optimization. The conditions producing the least error are summarized in Table 2. Error outputs are from a 2011-2015 river water level prediction using 100 randomly chosen data sets containing precipitation level, temperature, and previous river water level data from 2001-2015 fed to the neural network.

Table 4. Error outputs based on varied parameters

Number of Hidden Layers	5	10	15	20	25	30			
% error	2.4291	2.40743	2.4966	2.57209	7.11982	32.64183			
Number of Iterations	500	1000	1500	2000					
% error	2.46095	2.40743	2.40482	2.41998					
Learning Rate	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
% error	2.60339	2.40314	2.39228	2.39969	2.40743	2.49544	3.27784	6.13813	5.34459
Momentum Factor	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5				
% error	2.39228	2.39238	2.39395	2.40809	6.33613				

Table 5. Least percent errors produced based on different conditions

Number of Hidden Layers	10
% error	2.40743
Number of Iterations	1500
% error	2.40482
Learning Rate	0.3
% error	2.39228
Momentum Factor	0.1
% error	2.39228

Statistical analysis of the Results

A Pearson-correlation coefficient test was used to determine the strength of association between the predicted values of the neural network and the targeted values which are the actual data. A correlation coefficient of 0.3 or less would indicate little to no correlation. A value of 0.3 to 0.6 would indicate some correlation, and a value of 0.6 to 1.0 would indicate satisfactory or strong correlation. It will be used to conclude the viability of the neural network to make river water level predictions. Table 3 shows the correlation coefficient, r , based on the different optimization factors.

Table 6. r based on varied parameters

Number of Hidden Layers	5	10	15	20	25	30			
r	0.752002	0.778258	0.766464	0.767563	0.750643	0.46646			
Number of Iterations	500	1000	1500	2000					
r	0.773203	0.778258	0.774663	0.764203					
Learning Rate	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9
r	0.752145	0.771927	0.786156	0.757597	0.778258	0.761127	0.785076	0.757831	0.750811
Momentum Factor	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.4	0.5				
r	0.786156	0.775972	0.763675	0.778506	0.758995				

Table 4 summarizes the strongest correlations from the varied conditions. All conditions produced a correlation coefficient of 0.77 or better. The highest r was 0.786156 obtained by adjusting the momentum to 0.1.

Table 7. Best correlation coefficients produced based on different conditions

Number of Hidden Layers	10
r	0.778258
Number of Iterations	1500
r	0.778258
Learning Rate	0.3
r	0.785076
Momentum Factor	0.1
r	0.786156

The correlation coefficient of the predicted values of the neural network and the targeted values are relatively high throughout. The strong association suggests satisfactory ability of the artificial neural network to make predictions.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The artificial neural network developed was able to predict past river water level data with satisfactory accuracy. This is based on the most successful model that produced both minimal percent error and best correlation coefficient. This project was able to build a model that produces prediction values with high accuracy and fairly strong association in predicting 2011-2015 river water level data in the Sto. Nino Station of the Marikina River.

This suggests a potential for the ANN to be developed into a model that is able to make river water level prediction of satisfactory accuracy for the next years. It also supports the idea that it is possible to forecast river water level given historical and previous data, as well as other hydrological events such as water runoff or flooding.

Natural events caused by weather and meteorological factors such as river water level rise are caused by numerous factors that are variable and fluctuate easily thus, it is difficult to develop models that are able to predict with great accuracy. But, with proper equipment, adjustments, and data, neural network models have a great potential of being accurate and inexpensive forecast systems.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This project hopes to be a foundation for the development of better river water level prediction models. The limitations of the study may be exceeded through using proper data, performing better adjustments, and further development. We believe that feeding more inputs to the neural network that are also significant in the prediction such as elevation, air pressure, and humidity will improve the forecasting abilities of the model. Using data from more water level monitoring stations of a river will also extend the area spanned by the predictions.

Since neural networks involve tedious process control, it is also recommended that more parameters are adjusted and the data are separated into multiple groups before testing. The model may also be tested to make predictions for 2017 and the years after.

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